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Effectiveness of Visual Content on Social Media Marketing

Tuti Widiastuti

Department of Communication, Gunadarma University, Indonesia

Sukmariansi Vionnisa

Department of Communication, Gunadarma University, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to find out and analyze how effective visual content is in promotion strategies in the Industrial Revolution Era 4.0 on Instagram @Beanspot_id as well as knowing the respondents' responses about the level of awareness, comprehension, intention, interest, action on visual content in promotional strategies on Instagram @beanspot_id. This study used a quantitative method with a case study approach and a positivism paradigm. Data was obtained through the method of distributing online questionnaires, namely the Google Form which was carried out to 100 respondents with the criteria, namely followers of the Instagram account @beanspot_id. The results of this study reveal that through calculations using the Customer Response Index (CRI) method, which measures the effectiveness of visual content in promotional strategies in the industrial revolution era 4.0 on Instagram @beanspot_id, is less effective. The recommendation for Beanspot, especially the marketing team, to be able to explore more creative ideas and optimize more in terms of visualization so that they can attract new followers then increase the brand awareness, as well as the sales, especially on social media. For the development of further research, researchers provide suggestions using the CRI method on the Instagram Beanspot, which was declared to be ineffective, this could occur because of several factors, one of which is because there is a lot of competition via Instagram which is quite tight for similar coffee to go brands. Thus, the researcher's suggestion for Beanspot, especially the marketing team, is to be able to explore more creative ideas and optimize more in terms of visualization such as making quizzes with prizes that can attract new followers to increase brand awareness as well as being able to develop sales, especially on social media.

KEYWORDS: customer response index, digital promotion, social media marketing, visual content, Instagram

1. INTRODUCTION

Reported from the website keminfo.go.id, the minister of communication and informatics, Johnny Gerard Plate said that Indonesia is currently entering the era of the industrial revolution 4.0, in which changes in digital technology are increasingly massive. The industrial revolution 4.0 is characterized by a cyber-physical system, namely the combination of physical activities in the real world and virtual activities in the internet world. The extreme thing about industry 4.0 was mentioned by Fuchs, namely "an item is fully made, sent, used, repaired and recycled automatically through a network of various technologies via the internet without human intervention" (Fuchs, 2018: 281).

Conventional marketing concepts are adopted in digital marketing systems with various adjustments and with a fast process. The existence of internet technology makes many things that humans can do, such as socializing, getting, or sharing information, and even shopping, can be done via online. The way of interaction in marketing communications has changed to screen to digital marketing due to the rapid development of technology.

In the era of the digital revolution 4.0, the development of technology and the internet is used as an opportunity, one of which is digital marketing. A marketing communication intermediary tool that is currently widely used by social media in introducing products or services, one of which is by utilizing the media as a promotional tool is digital marketing. Digital marketing is the use of technology to assist marketing activities to increase customer knowledge according to their needs (Chaffey, 2013; Porsayev G, 2020:19-20).

In another definition, digital marketing uses technology of online marketing communications such as email, websites, digital TV, blogs, databases, podcasts, as well as social media. The application of this technology contributes to marketing activities carried out by business owners to develop relationships with consumers so that they can generate profits through a planned approach to increase consumer knowledge about brands, companies and products and then integrate these targets (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019).

Communication with online services according to a strategy developed by a particular company or brand owner. Meanwhile, social media is a media platform used by internet users to share experiences in the form of content using text, photos, or videos. As of January 2019, Indonesia's population is 268.2 million, and active social media users have reached 150 million users. Thus, more than 50% of Indonesia's population are social media users. This data is taken from the databoks.katadata.co.id survey. Based on the results of a survey by the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII), there are 210.03 million internet users in Indonesia in the 2021-2022 period, and the number of active

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social media users in Indonesia is 191 million people in January 2022, as obtained from the We Are Social report. Thus, Indonesia is a huge target for digital creative industry content.

Reported from Kompas.com, the most downloaded social media globally according to Data.ai is Instagram. Meanwhile, in Indonesia, the social media that has been downloaded the most is the TikTok application and Facebook is in second place, followed by Instagram in third place. According to research researched by Google's senior vice president who runs a knowledge and information organization, Prabhakar Raghavan, nearly 40 percent of young people rely more on TikTok and Instagram than Google. For example, when looking for references for lunch, instead of opening Google Maps or Google Search, young people prefer to look for it on TikTok or Instagram. Not only looking for places to eat, they also often use the application to shop online, continued Prabhakar Raghavan.

Many companies now use social media to promote their brands to maintain relationships with customers (Saravanakumar & Lakshmi, 2012: 4445). Reported from a journal entitled *How Instagram Can Be Used as a Tool in Social Network Marketing*, written by Lim Sook Huey and Rashad Yazdanifard Center for Southern New Hampshire University (SNHU) Programs HELP College of Art and Technology Kuala Lumpur Malaysia, an article published by BBC News (2012) said that many top brands around the world use Instagram as one of their marketing strategies. Instagram can help companies to promote a brand's product or service (Bevins, 2014: 37). The point that makes Instagram different from other social media is that Instagram implements a visual-based strategy (Hird, 2013: 5).

According to a journal entitled *Marketing engagement through visual content* written by Marius Manic, University of Braşov, visual content consists of three types, namely illustrations (images, photos, and memes), comics (images, text, or infographics) and videos (moving images). Reported from daily social.id, design can help build a business image and make it easier for customers to get information in content on social media, according to Amalia Nanda, a Content Lead of Nice to Meet You Studio (Arnetta, 2022). Amanda added that content design is not only social media aesthetics, but also a visual display for social media content and gives audiences a first impression.

Marketing on social media will create good customer engagement between customers and the company. The digital marketing process will create a separate experience for visitors. Therefore, if the marketing content is very interesting, it will certainly create customer engagement. More than 8.2 million creative businesses in Indonesia are dominated by culinary, fashion and craft businesses. In addition, there are 4 sub-sectors of the creative economy with the fastest growth, namely film, animation, and video, performing arts, and visual communication design. Thus, in the era of the digital revolution 4.0, this is a great opportunity for workers in the creative economy sector.

Seeing the great opportunities in this era, social media is increasingly in demand as a promotional event. PT Sumber Alfaria Trijaya, Tbk. successfully utilize social media to increase sales. Reported on the Alfamartku website, Alfamart was able to win the Social Media Award in 2014. The company that won the award is considered to have good sentiment as well as a share of voice on social media. One of the products from PT Sumber Alfaria Trijaya, Tbk, namely the coffee corner Beanspot which was released in 2020, also utilizes social media Instagram as a medium of promotion with an account called @beanspot_id which currently has 18.6 thousand followers.

Departing from the phenomenon above, this is interesting to be studied. As in the era of the digital revolution 4.0, the development of technology and the internet is increasing, so this phenomenon will open opportunities for the growth of new professions related to digital marketing, which will ultimately improve and develop the world of communication studies that has a close relationship with the creative economy industry, especially in the field of digital marketing. This research focuses more on studying "The Effectiveness of Visual Content in Promotional Strategies in the Industrial Revolution Era 4.0 on Instagram @beanspot_id".

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Hierarchy of Effects Theory was developed by Robert Lavidge and Gary Steiner (1961). Quoted from an e-book entitled *Encyclopedia of Communication theory* by Stephen W. Littlejohn. In the 1960s, Robert Lavidge and Gery Steiner challenged the direct selling and advertising effectiveness argument on the grounds that the effects of advertising were often long term and not necessarily translated into sales, for example, of brand image. According to (Robert Lavidge and Gery Steiner, 1961:19) there are seven steps in the consumer's journey to the point of purchase, namely unawareness, awareness, knowledge, favourable attitude toward the product, favourable attitude toward the brand, desire and conviction, and actual purchase. The hierarchy of effect theory states that different interactions between consumers and companies describe a journey through various stages that are getting closer to the advertiser's goal, namely selling products (Rehman et al., 2014 in Páramo et al, 2021: 20).

Promotion or marketing communication that involves mass media-based persuasive communication aimed at informing about the company's products or services and influencing the target audience (Moriarty et al. 2012 in Páramo et al, 2021: 20). At the end of the advertising, it is expected that the income is generated or at least the target market is increased (Lavidge and Steiner 1961 in Páramo et al, 2021: 20). The effect hierarchy model provides a more practical approach by including variables and constructs that are already available in the online marketing ecosystem (Florès, 2014 in Páramo et al, 2021: 20). This effect hierarchical model provides a systematic approach where each stage can be clearly identified and allows separate analysis of each stage (Bauman et al., 2008 in Páramo et al., 2021: 20). Quoted from a journal entitled "A Review and Critique of the Hierarchy of Effects in Advertising" by Thomas E. Barry & Daniel J. Howard, in DAGMAR (*Defining Advertising Goals for Measured Advertising Results*) by Colley (1961: 125) suggests that the hierarchy of objectives advertising should be used to develop and measure the effectiveness of advertising.

Advertising effectiveness is an advertising message that can attract attention, be known, be understood, arouse emotions, and move the target to provide the desired response from the extent to which the effect of the advertising message is conveyed (Effendi, 2002: 32-33). According to (Tsai & Tsai, 2006 in Ranjbarian, 2011: 230) advertising effectiveness is the effectiveness of communication in the sales process, which is measured by seeing and understanding, which can change attitudes as well as audience behaviour towards a product. Advertisements will have a high level of effectiveness and lead to the influence of audience attitudes, namely advertisements with images that are easy to remember (Grossman, et.al., 1998:23). Advertising effectiveness is determined by the creativity of the advertisement itself because it can capture

consumers' attention and make advertisements more memorable (Caples 1997, Kover 1995, Moriarty 1986, Reid et al. 1998 in Handoko, 2006 in Kurniawan, 2016: 4). Advertising effectiveness can be measured using many methods, namely: Media Mix Planning, DRM (Direct Rating Method), the developed EPIC Model, Customer Response Index, and Consumer Decision Model.

Reported from the website keminfo.go.id, the minister of communication and informatics, Johnny Gerard Plate said that currently Indonesia is entering the era of the industrial revolution 4.0, in which changes in digital technology are increasingly massive. The industrial revolution 4.0 is characterized by a cyber-physical system, namely the occurrence of a combination of physical activities in the real world and virtual activities in the internet world (Fuchs, 2018:281). The most extreme thing about industry 4.0 was mentioned by Fuchs, namely "an item that is completely made, sent, used, repaired and recycled automatically through a network of various technologies via the internet without human intervention". (Fuchs, 2018:281).

Through The Fourth Industrial Revolution Klaus (Shwab, 2016) states that the world has experienced four stages of revolution, namely: Industrial Revolution 1.0 which occurred in the 18th century through the invention of the steam engine, allowing goods to be mass-produced. The second Industrial Revolution 2.0 occurred in the 19-20th century with the presence of the use of electricity, which made production costs cheap. Next is the Industrial 3.0 revolution which occurred around the 1970s using computerization. The current era, namely the Industrial 4.0 revolution which occurred around the 2010s through artificial intelligence and the internet of thing as the backbone of movement and connecting humans and machines.

Manufacturing systems in the 4.0 industrial revolution that are operated digitally will also open up new market opportunities for SMEs providing technology such as sensors, robotics, 3D printing, or inter-machine communication technology. According to the Expert Staff of the Minister of Industry for Business and Investment Climate, Andi Rizaldi, the Industrial Revolution 4.0 will not eliminate jobs, but will offer new types of jobs that will allow people to move from one profession to another. In addition, the Director of Information and Communication for the Maritime Economy of the Ministry of Communication and Informatics, Septriana Tangkary, stated at the DigiTalk Forum event that a worker must have abilities that cannot be performed by machines and robots. These are problem solving skills, critical thinking, and creativity to be able to adapt to changes in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0.

Content according to KBBI Online is information that is available through media or electronic products. Content delivery can be done through various media, both directly and indirectly, such as the internet, television, audio CDs, or telephone. The form of content itself can be in the form of infographics, videos, or text. Creating diverse content will reach a wider audience.

The explanation regarding the content according to (Simarmata, 2010: 23) is the principal, type, or unit of digital information. Thus, contents can be interpreted as all things that can be managed in electronic format. Content marketing is content in the form of images, videos and audio that can create added value with the aim of promoting products/brands. Content marketing is used to promote brands by sharing useful content for visitors (Halvorson, 2010: 40). Quoted from a journal entitled Analysis of Riliw Instagram Post Visual Content in Forming Customer Engagement, written by Naura Firdaus Haidar, Martadi majoring in design, faculty of language and arts, Surabaya State University 2021, visual content is content that consists of visual or design components such as images that accompanied by articles or blogs will be a form of visual content. Examples for visual content itself are like Instagram feeds or infographics.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study used descriptive quantitative methods CRI or Customer Response Index. The data used by researchers are primary and secondary data. The data collection technique is by distributing questionnaires to respondents who are the subjects of the research. What is meant by quantitative research is a type of research that produces findings that can be obtained using statistical procedures or other means of quantification or measurement (Sujarweni, 2014:39). Descriptive research is research that describe a symptom, event, incident that is happening at the present time (Sujana & Ibrahim, 1989:64). The CRI Customer Response Index method is an analytical tool used to determine consumer response at a certain time for a brand's advertising campaign, in the form of a percentage, consumer responses in a questionnaire which is the multiplication of awareness, comprehend, interest, intention, action (Durianto, 2003: 10). The researcher chose descriptive quantitative research using the CRI method because with this type of research, the writer can objectively find out how effective visual content is in the promotion strategy on Instagram @beanspot_id, so that the data obtained is clearer and more specific.

The Customer Response Index is the result of multiplying awareness, comprehend, interest, intention, and action (Durianto et al, 2003: 48). This CRI method is used to measure the effectiveness of advertising in marketing communications. The stages in the response hierarchy in the Customer Response Index (CRI) (Caroline 2023, Durianto et al 2003, Shim 2003, Best 2012, Aiwan 2013, Gunawan 2014, Ernestivita 2016 in Aiwan, 2013: 302) are as follows:

1. Awareness is an effort to make consumers know or recognize a brand from an advertisement, sales promotion, or other marketing communication. The advertisement or promotion contains information to the public about the special features, benefits, advantages, and differences from competing brands.
2. Consumer understanding (Comprehend), consumer understanding of a brand in the form of marketing communications used.
3. Interest, namely consumer interest in a brand. In this dimension, the stage where potential consumers will determine whether they like or dislike a product.
4. Intention to buy, the stage where consumers intend to buy a product. The intended intention is something related to the consumer's plan to buy a certain product, as well as how many units of the product are needed in a certain period. Interest in buying can occur when there is interest and suitability between individual interests and benefits that can ultimately provide satisfaction after buying it.
5. Action is the stage where consumers take action to purchase a product. This stage is the last stage for marketers to quickly convince potential customers to take action to buy.

In this CRI analysis, responses from respondents will be categorized into two categories, namely negative answers marked with an answer of 0 (not at all) and positive response answers (answer score other than zero). By using the assumption that the responses obtained from respondents are based on the hierarchical influence assessment method.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

PT Sumber Alfaria Trijaya, Tbk presents a premium ready-to-drink coffee product with a contemporary style, namely Beanspot. Reported from destinationsbandung.co.id, Firty Firlandi, the Regional Corporate Communication Manager of Alfamart, said that the Beanspot segmentation is a modern urban consumer with a typical grab and go (take away) product that requires fast, select, and practical products.

Figure 2. Beanspot Logo
(Source: @beanspot on Instagram)

Beanspot comes with various variants of hot and cold premium coffee dishes with typical coffee flavours of various regions in Indonesia. Beanspot was introduced in May 2020, the coffee variants at Beanspot consist of iced doger coffee, teler iced coffee, klepon coffee, palm sugar coffee, to cheese coffee. The choice of a local-flavoured menu is aimed because they want to serve coffee that is close to Indonesian special drink. Beanspot also provides coffee variants such as cappuccino and mochaccino. Apart from coffee drinks, Beanspot is also equipped with ready-to-eat food products, including various breads, pastries, buns, and market snacks. The Beanspot coffee corner itself is located throughout Alfaexpress and Alfamart with the Beanspot logo.

Seeing this great opportunity in the digital 4.0 era, PT Sumber Alfaria Trijaya, Tbk. utilize social media to increase sales. Reported from the Alfamartku website, Alfamart was able to win the Social Media Award in 2014. The company that won the award is considered to have good sentiment as well as a share of voice on social media. One of the products from PT Sumber Alfaria Trijaya, Tbk, namely coffee corner Beanspot which was released in 2020, also utilizes social media Instagram as a medium of promotion with an account named @beanspot_id which currently has 18.6 thousand followers.

The @beanspot_id Instagram account posts visual content for product promotion purposes which also increases brand awareness. Figure 2 is a form of visual content that aims to promote its product. The picture shows the name of the product, the price of the product, there is also a call to action, namely a call to action for the audience that they display in one post, of course with the aim of increasing brand awareness. The visual content is in the form of Instagram stories, as shown in figure 2 the picture you can see the content is a kind of quiz, which refers to the knowledge of customers or @beanspot_id followers on Beanspot products. The visual content in the form of a quiz is of course aimed at brand awareness as well as product positioning.

Figure 3. Instagram Stories Visual Content

There are two variables in this study, Visual Content in the Promotion Strategy of the @Beanspot_id Instagram account as the independent variable (variable X) and effectiveness as the dependent variable (variable Y). The author uses questions in the form of dichotomous questions or Guttman scales. Dichotomous questions or the Guttman Scale in this study only provide two answer choices, namely “Yes” or “No”. The score for the answer “Yes” is given a value of 1 and “No” is given a value of 0. The author proceeds to the stage of processing the questionnaire data after getting 100 respondents, namely the number of samples needed in this study using SPSS (Statistic Product and Service Solution) version 22. Then the data that has been processed with SPSS will be analysed.

This study uses the Hierarchy of Effects Theory as the basis of the theory developed by Robert Lavidge and Gary Steiner (1961). The hierarchy of effect theory states that different interactions between consumers and companies describe a journey through various stages that are getting closer to the advertiser's goal, namely selling products (Rehman et al., 2014 in Páramo et al, 2021: 20). Robert Lavidge and Gery Steiner oppose the direct selling and advertising effectiveness argument on the grounds that the effects of advertising are often long term and do not always translate into sales such as brand image. Similar as the case in this study, that is, how is the consumer's journey to the point of purchase starting from building brand awareness through promotion with visual content on Instagram on the @Beanspot_id account. Then enter the Comprehend stage where followers understand the promotional strategy that is conveyed, then to the Interest stage where there is interest in the product being promoted, then Intention where there is an intention to buy the product being promoted which is the stage where followers act to buy Beanspot products.

Referring to the basic assumptions of the Hierarchy of Effects theory, the researcher quotes a statement in DAGMAR (Defining Advertising Goals for Measured Advertising Results) by Colley (1961: 125) suggesting that the hierarchy of advertising objectives should be used for developing and measuring advertising effectiveness. From this statement, the researchers conducted a method of measuring effectiveness using the CRI method.

Figure 4. Results of Measuring Effectiveness with CRI

Based on the results of the data in Figure 4 it shows that the results of 100 respondents at the awareness stage, as many as 27 respondents or 27% made the brand from Beanspot the most memorable coffee brand while the remaining 73 respondents or 73% did not remember or know the Beanspot brand. Furthermore, at the comprehend or consumer understanding stage, 77.5% understand the time of posting and promotion of each visual content post posted on Instagram @beanspot_id and the remaining 22.5% do not understand it. For the interest stage, 93.5% are interested in the Beanspot brand and 6.5% are not interested in products from this brand. Furthermore, the intention stage or intention to buy products from this brand is as much as 82% and the remaining 8% does not appear in the intention to buy products from the Beanspot brand. And for the last stage, namely the action stage or the action stage to buy Beanspot products, which is 79.5%, while for the no action stage, it is 20.5%. So the CRI is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{CRI} &= \text{awareness} \times \text{comprehend} \times \text{interest} \times \text{intention} \times \text{action} \\
 &= 27\% \times 77.5\% \times 93.5\% \times 82\% \times 79.5\% \\
 &= 12.75
 \end{aligned}$$

From the results of the CRI calculation above, a value of 12.75% is obtained, it can be interpreted that the effectiveness of visual content in the promotion strategy in the industrial revolution era 4.0 on Instagram @beanspot_id is less effective, this is obtained according to the reference to the value scale range as follows:

1. 1.00 – 33.00 = less effective
2. 34.00 – 66.00 = quite effective
3. 67.00 – 100.00 = very effective

In this study, the object of research is the effectiveness of visual content in promotion strategies. While the research subjects are the active Instagram followers @Beanspot_id. The research was conducted from March 2023 to July 2022 using an online questionnaire that was created on the Google form and distributed via DM (Direct Message). This study used a purposive sampling technique, the selection of which was based on criteria, namely followers of the @beanspot_id Instagram account. The process of determining the sample in this study used the Slovin formula and obtained 100 samples to fill out the research questionnaire.

There are several similarities as well as differences between this study and previous studies. The following is the equation of this study with the five previous studies. Using quantitative research methods with descriptive analysis techniques as well as CRI analysis methods. A similar research objective, which is to find out how much the value of effectiveness is in visual content or marketing content for Instagram accounts.

The following is the difference between this study and the five previous studies:

1. The first difference, of course, is in the variable in previous research. The first difference is in variable X, namely awareness, comprehend, intention, interest, action on Instagram adorable projects' visual content messages. Like the previous research, the second previous study had differences in variable X as well, namely content creators, then in the third previous study, the messages from Instagram food bloggers of the Surabaya millennial generation. Likewise in previous studies, the five differences were in variable X, namely the influence of content marketing. Meanwhile, in the previous research, the four differences were in variable Y, namely consumer awareness and building the image of Tobaku merchandise.
2. The next difference is in the research technique in one of the previous studies, namely using a survey technique with snowballing sampling, meanwhile in this study using a descriptive technique with purposive sampling.
3. The previous studies, the difference lies in the type of research, namely qualitative. The other difference is in the type of analysis, namely visual element analysis and awareness analysis, while in this study the CRI analysis technique was used which consisted of 5 stages, namely awareness, Comprehend, Interest, Intention, action.

In this study, the researcher divided the descriptions of respondents into two categories, namely based on gender and age. From the data that has been processed, the authors found that the category that was most owned by respondents was female, as much as 62% of respondents and the most age category was >20 years old, amounting to 85 respondents (85%). It was found that the statement that was filled in the most by respondents with the answer Yes was in statement number 4 of the photographic indicator, namely 98 respondents. This indicates that almost all respondents agree that the image on Instagram @beanspot_id represents an explanation of the promo being delivered. Then on the Y variable, it was found that the statement that was filled in the most by respondents was the Yes statement in question number 8 of the Comprehend indicator, namely as many as 98 respondents. This means that almost all respondents understand promotions for each post of visual content on the @beanspot_id Instagram.

Based on the results of the validity test, all variables with r count exceed the r table value, then the statement is declared valid and can be continued again in the next questionnaire. Thus, in the reliability test, because in this study using dichotomous answer choices for each item, the basic decision maker is, an instrument is said to be reliable if the value of the reliability coefficient KR is more than 0.70 ($r_i > 0.70$). This study obtained a value of 0.766 so that all variables are declared reliable.

Next, the researcher conducts a classic assumption test in which there is a normality test, and a heteroscedasticity test. In the normality test, the asymptotic value is significant by 0.000. This statement means that the asymptotic value is significantly less than 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that the data is not normally distributed. However, the researcher switched to a nonparametric test, the Spearman rank correlation test, due to the possibility of random samples or values that were too extreme. And from the test results using the Spearman rank correlation test, the significance value is 0.000 which according to the basis of decision making if the significance value is <0.05 then it correlates and vice versa. Thus, it can be concluded that the data is significantly correlated between variable X and variable Y. And based on the heteroscedasticity test, the output image obtained from the scatterplot with dots spreads in an unclear pattern, and data points spread above and below or around zero on the Y variable. Thus, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem, and a good research model can be fulfilled.

After that, the authors conducted a simple linear regression test with the aim of testing whether the visual content variable as a promotional strategy in the 4.0 industrial revolution era on Instagram @Beanspot_id is linearly related to the effectiveness variable. And get the result that the visual content variable as a promotional strategy in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 on Instagram @Beanspot_id is linearly related to the effectiveness variable. In every visual content in this @beanspot_id Instagram post will increase the effectiveness of the promotion strategy in the industrial revolution 4.0 era by 79.6%.

Referring to the basic assumptions of the theory of the Hierarchy of Effects where the hierarchy of advertising objectives must be used to develop and measure the effectiveness of advertising, so researchers conducted a method of measuring effectiveness using the CRI (Customer Response Index) method. In this measurement, the percentage of respondents who reached the stage of buying Beanspot products was 12.75%, then the remaining 87.25% CRI can still be achieved by Beanspot. Those are already aware of the brand, fascinated, interested have not taken action to buy and consume Beanspot products.

After testing the hypothesis, the authors tested the coefficient of determination with the aim of measuring how far the ability of the analysis model made to explain the variation in the dependent variable. The magnitude of the correlation value (R) is 0.384. This means that the relationship between variables (X), namely the visual content in the promotional strategy on Instagram @Beanspot, to the variable (Y), namely effectiveness, is 0.384 (38%). The conclusion that between variables (X) and (Y) there is a moderate relationship. The coefficient of determination (R square) is 0.147, which means that the effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) is 14.7%, while the remaining 85.3% is influenced by other factors outside of this study.

Furthermore, the researcher tested the hypothesis with the t-test, which was used to see whether the independent variable, namely the visual content variable in the promotion strategy on Instagram @beanspot_id had a positive and significant effect on the dependent variable, namely effectiveness. Based on the t-test, it can be said that the hypothesis is accepted.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the research and results of the analysis that has been carried out which is supported by the theory obtained from existing references, with the aim of knowing how effective visual content is in Promotional strategies in the Industrial Revolution Era 4.0 on Instagram @Beanspot_id. As well as knowing the respondents' responses about the level of awareness, comprehend, intention, interest, action on visual

content in the Promotion strategy on Instagram @Beanspot_id, and it can be concluded that the effectiveness of visual content in the promotion strategy using the Customer Response Index (CRI) method on the @beanspot_id Instagram account declared less effective. The following is an explanation of the percentage of results from respondents based on the five dimensions of CRI:

Awareness percentage of 27% makes the brand from Beanspot the most memorable coffee brand, while the remaining 73% do not remember or know the brand. It can be seen from the percentage that most of the respondents are unaware of the Beanspot brand. There is a lot of competition between coffee brands that are similar, especially those that promote through visual content on Instagram, so that the Beanspot brand must optimize the way it is promoted on Instagram social media so that potential followers or followers are increasingly aware of the Beanspot brand.

The comprehend percentage of 77.5% understands the time of posting and promotion of each post of visual content posted on Instagram @beanspot_id and the remaining 22.5% do not understand it. So, when viewed from the percentage, it is more dominated that respondents understand the time of posting and understand every promotion posted on Instagram @beanspot. It seems that the level of understanding of @beanspot Instagram post time should be more consistent. Furthermore, the level of understanding of promotions conveyed through visual content should also be increased, because seeing very tight competition, the marketing team must develop the appearance of Instagram Beanspot visual content to make it more attractive.

The percentage of interest as much as 93.5% is interested in the Beanspot brand after seeing visual content posts on Beanspot Instagram and 6.5% are not interested in products from this brand. So, when viewed from the average percentage, it is more dominated by respondents who are interested in the product delivered by the Instagram account @beanspot through its visual content.

The percentage of Intention is 82% and the remaining 8% has no intention to buy products from the Beanspot brand. It is more dominated that respondents have the intention to buy a product after seeing a promotion in the form of visual content posted on Instagram beanspot. The percentage of action is 79.5%, while 20.5% have no action to buy products or recommend Beanspot products after seeing promotions in the form of visual content posted on Instagram beanspot. So, if it is seen from the average percentage, it is more dominated that respondents take action to buy products from beanspot after seeing promotions in the form of visual content posted on Instagram Beanspot.

According to the data described above, the researcher can draw the conclusion that through calculations using the CRI method which measures the effectiveness of visual content in promotion strategies in the industrial revolution era 4.0 on Instagram @beanspot_id it can be said to be less effective. This is obtained by multiplying the results of awareness, comprehension, interest, intention, and action and gets a percentage of 12.75% according to the scale range that has been set at 1.00 – 33.00 which is said to be less effective.

Looking at the results of research conducted using the CRI method on the Instagram Beanspot account, which was declared to be ineffective, this could occur because of several factors, one of which is because there is a lot of competition via Instagram which is quite tight for similar coffee to go brands. Thus, the researcher's suggestion for Beanspot, especially the marketing team, is to be able to explore more creative ideas and optimize more in terms of visualization such as making quizzes with prizes that can attract new followers to increase brand awareness as well as being able to develop sales, especially on social media.

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